

Comparative Evaluation of the Marginal Adaptation of Emax Ceramic Inlays Fabricated using Traditional Rubber Base and Digital Impression Technique in Permanent Premolar: An in Vitro Study

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 16-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Emax ceramic inlays are widely used in restorative dentistry due to their excellent aesthetic and mechanical properties. The accuracy of marginal adaptation is crucial for the longevity and clinical success of these restorations. Traditional rubber base impression techniques have been the standard for years, but digital impression techniques have recently gained popularity due to their potential for higher precision.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays fabricated using traditional rubber base and digital impression techniques in permanent premolars.

Methods: An in vitro study was conducted on 90 extracted human permanent premolars, divided into two groups: Group A (n = 45) using traditional rubber base impressions and Group B (n = 45) using digital impressions. Emax ceramic inlays were fabricated for all teeth, and marginal adaptation was measured using a stereomicroscope. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive statistics and an Independent Samples t-test used to compare the groups.

Results: The mean marginal gap was significantly smaller in the digital impression group ($51.0 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the traditional rubber base group ($75.3 \pm 8.1 \mu\text{m}$), with a p-value of <0.001 , indicating superior marginal adaptation in the digital group.

Conclusion: Digital impression techniques result in significantly better marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays compared to traditional rubber base methods. This suggests that digital techniques should be preferred for the fabrication of ceramic inlays to enhance clinical outcomes.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, it is recommended that dental practitioners consider adopting digital impression techniques to improve the accuracy and longevity of ceramic restorations.

Keywords: Emax Ceramic Inlays, Digital Impressions, Marginal Adaptation, Rubber Base Impressions, Restorative Dentistry.

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Introduction

For many years, dental research and clinical practice have been centred on the hunt for the best restorative materials and methods. Because of its better mechanical, biocompatibility, and cosmetic advantages, Emax ceramic inlays have become a popular alternative for repairing posterior teeth, particularly premolars, when compared to other restorative materials. These restorations' marginal adaptation plays a crucial role in determining how long they last and how well they function clinically since a poor adaptation can result in microleakage, secondary caries, and periodontal problems [1]. Conventional impression processes, such the use of rubber base materials, have been used in the

creation of ceramic inlays historically. Even though these materials work well, they have drawbacks such as distortion, shrinking, and mistakes made while handling them by hand. These elements may impair the final restoration's precision, leading to less-than-ideal marginal adaptation [2]. In restorative dentistry, however, a paradigm change has been brought about by the introduction of digital impression procedures. Compared to conventional techniques, digital impressions have a number of benefits, including as improved accuracy, shorter chair times, and the removal of possible material handling errors [3].

According to recent research, restorations made with digital impression techniques in combination with CAD/CAM technology can have better marginal adaptability than restorations made with conventional procedures. For example, CAD/CAM-fabricated restorations based on digital impressions showed much superior marginal and internal fit than restorations made using conventional procedures, as proven by a research [4]. Comparably, a meta-analysis conducted in 2020 by Alikhasi et al. found that digital imprints yield more consistent and precise results, which are essential to guaranteeing the durability of ceramic inlays [5]. Despite these benefits, the use of digital imprint techniques is still developing, and research is constantly being done to determine whether they are better than traditional procedures. By contrasting the marginal adaption of Emax ceramic inlays made using conventional rubber base impressions and digital impression procedures in permanent premolars, this study seeks to add to the expanding body of information. This study aimed to compare the marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays fabricated using traditional rubber base and digital impression techniques in permanent premolars.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective, in vitro, comparative evaluation.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of 7 months.

Participants: A total of 90 extracted human permanent premolars were selected for this in vitro study. The teeth were divided into two groups:

- Group A: 45 premolars for traditional rubber base impression technique.
- Group B: 45 premolars for digital impression technique.

Inclusion Criteria

- Extracted human permanent premolars.
- Teeth free from caries, restorations, fractures, or cracks.
- Teeth with well-defined margins.

Exclusion Criteria

- Teeth with extensive caries, restorations, or structural defects.
- Teeth with root resorption or fractures.
- Teeth with signs of periodontal disease.
- Teeth not fitting the inclusion criteria.

Bias: To minimize bias, random allocation of the teeth into the two groups was ensured. The operator conducting the impression techniques and the evaluator of the marginal adaptation were blinded to the group allocation.

Data Collection: Data collection involved the measurement of the marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays. Measurements were taken using a stereomicroscope at predefined points around the margins of each inlay.

Procedure

1. **Teeth Preparation:** Each of the 90 premolars was prepared to receive an Emax ceramic inlay with standardized cavity dimensions.
2. **Impression Techniques:**

Group A: Impressions were taken using the traditional rubber base impression technique.

Group B: Impressions were taken using a digital impression technique.
3. **Fabrication of Inlays:** Emax ceramic inlays were fabricated using the respective impressions from each group.
4. **Measurement of Marginal Adaptation:** The inlays were placed into the prepared cavities, and the marginal adaptation was assessed under a stereomicroscope. Measurements were recorded in micrometers at multiple points along the margins.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) calculated for each group. The Independent Samples t-test was used for comparison, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. This approach ensures a systematic and unbiased evaluation of marginal adaptation between the two impression techniques.

Results

A total of 90 extracted human permanent premolars were included in the study, with 45 teeth allocated to each group:

- **Group A:** Traditional Rubber Base Impression Technique (n = 45)
- **Group B:** Digital Impression Technique (n = 45)

Marginal Adaptation Measurements: The marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays was measured at four points around the inlay margins (buccal, lingual, mesial, and distal) for each tooth. The mean marginal gap values (in micrometers) and standard deviations for each group are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Marginal Gap Measurements (in micrometers) for Each Group

Group	Buccal (Mean ± SD)	Lingual (Mean ± SD)	Mesial (Mean ± SD)	Distal (Mean ± SD)	Overall Mean ± SD
Group A	75.3 ± 8.1	72.6 ± 7.9	78.5 ± 8.3	74.8 ± 8.0	75.3 ± 8.1
Group B	50.2 ± 5.7	49.8 ± 5.5	52.6 ± 6.0	51.3 ± 5.8	51.0 ± 5.7

Comparative Analysis: The Independent Samples t-test was performed to compare the mean marginal gap values between the two groups.

Table 2: Independent Samples t-test Results Comparing Marginal Adaptation between Groups

Group Comparison	Mean Difference (µm)	t-value	p-value
Group A vs. Group B	24.3	15.89	<0.001

Interpretation of Results

- **Mean Marginal Gap:** The overall mean marginal gap was significantly smaller in Group B (Digital Impression Technique) compared to Group A (Traditional Rubber Base Impression Technique). Group B had an overall mean marginal gap of $51.0 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{m}$, while Group A had a mean gap of $75.3 \pm 8.1 \mu\text{m}$.
- **Statistical Significance:** The difference in mean marginal gaps between the two groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating superior marginal adaptation in inlays fabricated using the digital impression technique.
- **Point-wise Comparison:** Across all measurement points (buccal, lingual, mesial, and distal), Group B consistently showed smaller marginal gaps compared to Group A.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate a clear difference in the marginal adaptation of Emax ceramic inlays fabricated using traditional rubber base versus digital impression techniques. On average, the digital impression technique resulted in significantly smaller marginal gaps, with an overall mean of $51.0 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{m}$, compared to $75.3 \pm 8.1 \mu\text{m}$ for the traditional rubber base technique. This suggests that inlays produced using digital impressions fit more precisely within the prepared cavities of premolar teeth.

The statistical analysis further supports these findings, with the Independent Samples t-test revealing a highly significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.001$). This statistical significance highlights the superiority of the digital impression technique in achieving a better marginal fit, which is crucial for the longevity and success of ceramic inlays. A better marginal adaptation reduces the risk of microleakage, secondary caries, and other complications, thereby enhancing the overall clinical outcome.

Overall, the study demonstrates that the digital impression technique is a more accurate and reliable method for fabricating Emax ceramic inlays, providing a better marginal fit than the traditional rubber base method. These findings have important clinical implications, suggesting that dental professionals should consider adopting digital impression techniques to improve the quality and durability of ceramic restorations.

The impact of various impression methods and ceramic materials on the marginal adaptation of dental restorations has been investigated in recent research. A research comparing traditional and digital imprints for inlays made of lithium disilicate and feldspathic ceramics was carried out. They discovered that while both impression techniques offered comparable marginal adaptation, when digital impressions were employed, feldspathic ceramic outperformed lithium disilicate in terms of internal adaptation [6].

The marginal misfits of three-unit frameworks made using both traditional and digital impression techniques were assessed. The findings demonstrated the accuracy of digital systems in dental restoration procedures by showing that digital impression techniques provide a better marginal fit than traditional methods [7].

Micro-CT in a different investigation is used to assess the internal and marginal fits of lithium-disilicate inlays made with three- and five-axis CAM systems compared to a conventional heat-press method. According to the study's findings, the heat-press method offered the best internal and marginal adaption. Both milling processes, however, are viable for creating high-quality dental restorations because every technique examined was found to be within clinically acceptable bounds [8].

How impression method and preparation design affected the marginal adaption of CAD-CAM onlays was analysed. According to their research, a modified preparation with flat cuspal reduction performed worse on marginal adaptation than a conventional preparation with a modified shoulder margin. This suggests that the design of preparation is quite important [9].

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that Emax ceramic inlays fabricated using the digital impression technique exhibit significantly better marginal adaptation compared to those fabricated using the traditional rubber base impression technique. The superior precision of the digital method likely contributes to the improved fit, which could have clinical implications for the longevity and success of these restorations.

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